

1 Experimental study on the settling motion 2 of coral grains in still water

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14 Understanding settling motion of coral grains is important since the settled grains can be
15 threats to the coral reef community. In this paper, a series of laboratory experiments were
16 conducted to investigate the settling motion, using optical microscopy to measure shape
17 parameters of coral grains and the particle-filtering-based object tracking to reconstruct
18 the three-dimensional trajectory. Three characteristic descent regimes, namely, tumbling,
19 chaotic and fluttering, are classified based on the **three-dimensional** trajectory, the spiral
20 radius variation and the velocity spectrum. It is demonstrated that if one randomly picks **up**
21 one coral grain, **then** the probabilities of occurrence of the three regimes are **approximately**
22 26 %, 42 % and 32 %, respectively. We have shown that **first**, the dimensionless settling
23 velocity generally increases with the non-dimensional diameter D^* and Corey shape factor
24 S_f , and **second**, the drag coefficient generally decreases with the Reynolds number (Re)
25 **and** S_f . Based on this, the applicability of existing models on predicting settling velocity
26 and drag coefficient for coral grains is **demonstrated further**. Finally, we have proposed
27 extended models for predicting the settling velocity. This study contributes to better
28 understanding of settling motion and improves our predictive capacity of settling velocity
29 for coral grains with complex geometry.

30 **Key words:** sediment transport

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31 1. Introduction

Q5 32 Coral reef sediments have important implications for coral reef ecosystems. These
 33 sediments can provide the community (including reefs, fleshy algae and fish) with
 34 necessary carbonate and nutrients (Dong *et al.* 2023). However, with increased human
 35 activity, coral reef sediments are now even being considered as threats to the coral
 36 reef systems. Intense hydrodynamic disturbances e.g. typhoons (Pratchett 2005), blast
 37 fishing and illegal poaching of tridacna (Scales, Balmford & Manica 2007) can cause
 38 suspension of sediments (Jones *et al.* 2016; Rogers & Ramos-Scharrón 2022). These
 39 suspended sediments can settle directly on corals and other reef organisms, which will
 40 smother and abrade corals (Jones *et al.* 2016; Rogers & Ramos-Scharrón 2022). The
 41 suspended sediments can also reduce the coral photosynthesis by blocking light. The
 42 velocity of settling has been shown to influence the attachment and survival rates of
 43 coral larvae (Babcock & Smith 2002; Rogers & Ramos-Scharrón 2022). Understanding
 44 of settling motion and having predictive capacity for the settling velocity are critical in
 45 terms of helping to protect coral reef systems from those threats and restore the ecosystems
 Q6 46 effectively.

47 The settling motion has been explored in detail for a circular disk and a sphere with
 48 uniform shape but not for coral grains. For a circular disk, three regimes of settling
 49 trajectory were classified in Field *et al.* (1997), namely, fluttering, chaotic and tumbling.
 50 It has been demonstrated that the settling trajectory is highly dependent on the object
 51 geometry (Maiklem 1968). For a sphere, more fruitful regimes were observed (Raaghav,
 52 Poelma & Breugem 2022). In reality, the biological structure of coral grains makes their
 53 geometry more complicated than the disk and sphere (Wang *et al.* 2020), which increases
 54 the complexity of settling motion (de Kruijf *et al.* 2021). Understanding the settling motion
 55 of coral grains is one of motivations of this study.

56 In the settling motion, when the effective force is equal to the drag force on the particle
 57 in the vertical direction (over the depth), the particle will fall with an equilibrium settling
 58 velocity ω . Different empirical models have been proposed for predicting the setting
 59 velocity for particles from different sources. For natural quartz, the model in Dietrich
 60 (1982) established the relationship of dimensionless velocity W^* with the non-dimensional
 61 particle diameter D^* (W^* and D^* are parameters non-dimensionalised by Reynolds number
 62 and drag coefficient). This relationship was then extended to carbonate grains in Li *et al.*
 63 (2020). Similarly, a semi-empirical model was proposed in Riazi *et al.* (2020) for carbonate
 64 sediments, in which the settling velocity is a function of S (the specific gravity of the
 65 particle), C_D (the drag coefficient), S_f (the Corey shape factor) and D_n (the nominal
 66 diameter). In comparison to these models, the model in Alcerreca, Silva & Mendoza
 67 (2013) simply established the relationship between Re and D^* (ω is embedded in Re).

68 In comparison to settling velocity, there is also a range of models that can be used to
 69 estimate the drag coefficient C_D . First, the drag coefficient of a coral grain can be estimated
 70 through direct measurements of settling velocity, densities of coral grain and fluid, and the
 71 geometry of the grain. The drag coefficient can also be evaluated through the empirical
 72 model of Riazi *et al.* (2020), which links C_D to the nominal diameter and the kinematic
 73 viscosity of fluid. Finally, the drag coefficient can be predicted by the model of Wang *et al.*
 74 (2018), in which C_D is a function of Reynolds number and the shape factor defined in their
 75 study.

76 Although different models of settling velocity and drag coefficient have been developed
 77 in literature, grain shape parameters in these models still rely on some kind of
 78 approximation of spherical or tri-axial geometries. These approximated parameters
 79 sometimes are not that representative to the real geometry of coral grains. Since both

80 settling velocity and drag coefficient are highly dependent on the grain geometry (Maiklem
81 1968), applying these models to real systems can be problematic if the targeted grains are
82 very different from the unknown particles used in the validation of the empirical models.
83 This highlights the importance of using coral grains with fully categorised, quantified
84 geometry to validate existing empirical models. In such a way, the applicable range of
85 validated/modified models is well defined.

86 There is a range of approaches used to classify coral reef grains. For simplicity of
87 classification, the coral grains were normally simplified into an ellipsoid (Wadell 1932;
88 Krumbein 1941; Oakey *et al.* 2005). The long, medium and short axes of the ellipsoid
89 (D_l , D_m and D_s were found to be important dimensions in the classification. Based on
90 the dimensionless variables D_m/D_l and D_s/D_m , coral grains were classified into four
91 sub-populations, namely, discord, blade, rod and spheroid (Zingg 1935). In contrast, based
92 on a combined parameter set (D_m/D_l , D_s/D_l and $(D_l - D_m)/(D_l - D_s)$), the sediments
93 can be categorised into four types: platy, bladed, elongated and compact (Sneed & Folk
94 1958). In comparison to these two classification methods based on the simplification of
95 ellipsoid, there is another approach proposed in Wang *et al.* (2020). This approach was
96 established based on second-order shape descriptors.

97 In the light of existing work, this paper aims to investigate the settling motion of 222
98 coral grains from the South China Sea, with three specific objectives: (1) categorise these
99 coral grains; (2) classify the settling trajectory of coral grains; (3) validate and extend
100 existing models for predicting settling velocity and drag coefficient.

101 2. Methodology

102 2.1. Geometric parameters

103 There are three orders of the scale for describing the shapes of irregular particles (figure 1):
104 form, roughness and surface texture (Griffiths 1967; Barrett 1980). However, limited by the
105 availability of measuring equipment, most studies on shape quantification have focused on
106 the first and second scales. In the first order of scale, form is the fundamental descriptor
107 of the three-dimensional spatial distribution of a particle in space. As shown in figure 2,
108 the lengths of three axes (i.e. long axis D_l , intermediate axis D_m , and short axis D_s) of
109 the ellipsoid can characterise the three-dimensional spatial distribution of the particle
110 (Barrett 1980; Oakey *et al.* 2005; Blott & Pye 2008; Heilbronner & Barrett 2013). Based
111 on these dimensions, several dimensionless parameters are used to describe the form of
112 the particles, such as the flatness D_s/D_m (Blott & Pye 2008), elongation D_m/D_l (Lüttig
113 1956), and equancy D_s/D_l (Illenberger 1991). Meanwhile, Wadell (1932, 1933) and Corey
114 *et al.* (1949) defined the nominal diameter and the Corey shape factor, respectively, for the
115 non-spherical grains as

$$116 \quad D_n = \sqrt[3]{D_l D_m D_s}, \quad (2.1)$$

$$117 \quad S_f = \frac{D_s}{\sqrt{D_l D_m}}. \quad (2.2)$$

118 In the second order of scale, roundness characterises the smoothness of the particles.
119 Establishing the shape parameters at the roundness scale is usually achieved by quantifying
120 the difference of the grain shape from the spherical shape (see figure 3) with the sphericity
121 ϕ , a ratio between surface area $A_{eq, sph}$ of a sphere and that of the particle A_p (the sphere
122 has the same volume as the particle). However, the shape of coral sand particles is complex
123 at the roundness scale (figure 1) due to the deposition processes in coral islands and

Figure 1. Shape descriptors of three orders for a coral grain.

Figure 2. Tri-axial orthogonal system of the ellipsoid simplification of a real coral grain.

124 the presence of skeletal structures (Slootman *et al.* 2023). These parameters may not
 125 be sufficient to describe the geometry of coral particles. To address this, a new shape
 126 parameter ψ was proposed in Wang *et al.* (2018) for describing the highly irregular grains,
 127 which is defined as

$$128 \quad \psi = \frac{\phi}{X}, \quad \phi = \frac{A_{eq, sph}}{A_p}, \quad X = \frac{P_{p, max}}{P_{eq}}, \quad (2.3a-c)$$

129 where ϕ is sphericity, $A_{eq, sph} = \pi(D_{eq, sph})^2$ is the surface area of the volume-equivalent
 130 sphere, $D_{eq, sph} = ((6/\pi)V_p)^{1/3}$ is the diameter of the volume-equivalent sphere,
 131 V_p is the particle volume, A_p is the surface area [which is calculated as
 132 $A_p \approx A_{ell} = \pi[(D_l D_m)^\kappa + (D_l D_s)^\kappa + (D_m D_s)^\kappa / 3]^{1/\kappa}$, with $\kappa = 1.6075$], A_{ell} is the
 133 surface area of the irregular particles under the tri-axial orthogonal system of the ellipsoid
 134 (figure 2), $P_{p, max}$ is the perimeter of the maximum projection area of the particle, and P_{eq}
 135 is the perimeter of a circle with the same maximum projection area as the particle.

136 The original classification method based on the first-order shape descriptors (figure 4)
 137 was unable to describe the particular shape of the coral sand grains (see figure 1) due to the
 138 complexity of the particle shape. Wang *et al.* (2019) summarised a series of the first-order
 139 and second-order shape descriptors from the studies of Mora & Kwan (2000), Kwan,
 140 Mora & Chan (1999) and Hentschel & Page (2003). Wang *et al.* (2019) then classified
 141 coral grains into dendrites, rods, flakes and blocks based on some second-order shape

Figure 3. Diagram of shape descriptors reported in Wang *et al.* (2019).

Q10 Figure 4. Irregular particle classification based on the first-order shape descriptors: (a) classification diagram from Zingg (1935) and (b) equant-oblate-prolate ternary classification diagram by Sneed & Folk (1958).

142 descriptors (tables 2 and 3). These descriptors based on three dimensions were determined
 143 with multi-photographs taken from different angles of view.

144 2.2. Predictive models of drag coefficient and settling velocity

145 2.2.1. Models for estimating C_D

146 (i) Model I_D (direct measurement)

147 When the effective weight force is equal to the drag force of particle in the vertical
 148 direction, the particle falls with terminal settling velocity. At this stage, the force in
 149 the vertical direction (over depth) can be expressed as

$$150 (\rho_s - \rho)gV = \frac{1}{2}\rho C_D A_P \omega^2, \quad (2.4)$$

151 where ρ_s and ρ are the densities of coral grain and fluid, respectively, g is the
 152 gravitational acceleration, V is the volume of the coral grain, C_D is the drag
 153 coefficient, A_P is the maximum projected area of the particle, and ω is the particle

Parameter	Description	2-D definition	3-D definition
Area	A	Area of image	Mean A value of a series of images
Perimeter	C_i	Perimeter of image	Mean C_i value of a series of images
Convex area	C_A	Area of minimum convex hull	Mean C_A value of a series of images
Convex perimeter	C_P	Perimeter of minimum convex hull	Mean C_P value of a series of images
Feret diameter	F_a	Distance between two parallel tangents of the particle at an arbitrary angle	—
Length	L	Maximum Feret diameter	Maximum length in a series of images
Width	W	Width	Maximum width in a series of images
Thickness	T	—	Minimum width in a series of images
Diameter of a circle of equal projection area	D_A	Diameter of a circle that has the same area as the projection area of the particle	Mean D_A value of a series of images
Diameter of a circle of equal perimeter	D_P	Diameter of a circle that has the same perimeter as the image	Mean D_P value of a series of images

Q9 Table 1. Two-dimensional (2-D) and three-dimensional (3-D) first-order shape descriptors.

Parameter	Description	Formula
Superficial area	S_A	Area of image
Superficial area of convex hull	S_{CA}	Perimeter of image
Volume	V_{ch}	Area of minimum convex hull
Convexity ratio	S_0	$S_0 = A/C_A$
Roundness	R_0	$R_0 = 4A/(\pi L^2)$
Width-to-thickness ratio	W/T	—
Elongation ratio	L/W	—
Relative sphericity	S_P	$S_P = D_A/D_P$
Convex ratio	C_0	$C_0 = C_P/P$

Table 2. Particle shape parameters in Wang *et al.* (2019).

Parameter	Rod	Flake	Dendrite	Block
Elongation ratio	>1.8	—	—	Others
Width-to-thickness ratio	<1.8	>1.8	>1.2	
Relative sphericity	—	—	<0.76	
Roundness	>0.85	>0.85	<0.85	

Table 3. Classification criteria for calcium sand with various shapes in Wang *et al.* (2019).

154 settling velocity. Equation (2.4) can be rewritten in the form

$$155 \quad C_D = 2 \frac{(S - 1)g}{\omega^2} \frac{V}{A_P}, \quad (2.5)$$

156 where $S = \rho_s/\rho$ is the specific gravity of the particle. The drag coefficient can be
157 determined by measuring all the quantities on the right-hand side of (2.5).

158 (ii) **Model II_D (Riazi et al. 2020)**

159 Based on the data of Smith & Cheung (2002), Riazi et al. (2020) used a genetic
160 algorithm (Riazi & Türker 2018) to obtain an expression for C_D of coral grains:

$$161 \quad C_D = \left(\frac{9.50 \times \nu}{D_n^{1.5} \times g^{0.5}} + 0.76 \right)^{2.92} + \left(\frac{20.47 \times \nu}{D_n^{1.5} \times g^{0.5}} + 1.02 \right)^{-48.15}, \quad (2.6)$$

162 where ν is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid.

163 (iii) **Model III_D (Wang et al. 2018)**

164 Wang et al. (2018) obtained the relationship between drag coefficient and Reynolds
165 number based on experimental data of 521 calcareous sand particles, which is
166 expressed by

$$167 \quad \left. \begin{aligned} C_D &= 0.945 \frac{C_{D, sph}}{\psi^f(Re)} Re^{-0.01}, \\ C_{D, sph} &= \frac{24}{Re} \left(1 + 0.15 Re^{0.687} \right) + 0.42 \left/ \left(1 + \frac{42500}{Re^{1.16}} \right) \right., \\ f(Re) &= 0.641 Re^{0.153}, \\ Re &= \frac{\rho \omega D_n}{\mu}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.7)$$

168 2.2.2. Models for predicting setting velocity

169 (i) **Model I_V (Riazi et al. 2020)**

170 Using an approximation of ellipsoids to natural particles, Riazi et al. (2020) found
171 that the ratio of the volume V to the projected area A_P is a function of S_f and D_n ,
172 with the relationship

$$173 \quad \frac{V}{A_P} = \alpha \frac{4}{6} S_f^{2/3} D_n, \quad (2.8)$$

174 where $\alpha = 0.55$ based on their experimental data. The derivation of (2.8) was
175 based on extensive observations that natural particles will adjust themselves into a
176 state where the maximum projected area ($A_p = \pi D_l D_m / 4$) is normal to the settling
177 direction, regardless of the orientation of the particle being realised into fluid
178 (Dietrich 1982; Alldredge & Gotschalk 1988; Khatmullina & Isachenko 2017; Riazi
179 & Türker 2019). Equation (2.8) was validated by measuring variables on both sides
180 of this equation, which gives measured values of α . The root mean square error
181 (RMSE) between the measured values of α and 0.55 determined by Riazi et al.
182 (2020) is 32.5 % for our 222 coral grains, which supports the applicability of this
183 equation to the present study. Q11

184 Equation (2.4) can be rewritten as

$$185 \quad \omega^2 = 2 \frac{(S-1)g}{C_D} \frac{V}{A_P}. \quad (2.9)$$

186 Combining (2.8) with (2.9) gives

$$187 \quad \omega^2 = \alpha \frac{4}{3} \frac{(S-1)g}{C_D} S_f^{2/3} D_n. \quad (2.10)$$

188 Note that C_D is unknown in (2.10). In practice, this model needs to be combined
189 with the drag model II_D to provide a closed-form solution for both the velocity and
190 the drag coefficient.

191 (ii) **Model II_V (Dietrich 1982)**

192 Many researchers (Rouse *et al.* 1938; Schulz, Wilde & Albertson 1954; Dietrich
193 1982) have described the settling velocity in a dimensionless form of W^* as

$$194 \quad W^* = \left[\left(\frac{4}{3} \right) \frac{Re}{C_{D, sph}} \right]^{-1/3} = \omega [vg(S-1)]^{-1/3}. \quad (2.11)$$

Q12 195 By analogy, the particle diameter was also expressed as

$$196 \quad D^* = \left[\frac{3}{4} (Re)^2 C_{D, sph} \right]^{1/3} = D \left[\left(\frac{1}{v} \right)^2 g(S-1) \right]^{1/3}. \quad (2.12)$$

197 Dietrich (1982) collected a large amount of experimental data of natural silicate
198 particles and proposed a model of settling velocity based on particle shape
199 characteristics (particle size D^* , particle shape S_f , particle roughness P):

$$200 \quad \left. \begin{aligned} W^* &= R_3 10^{R_1 + R_2}, \\ R_1 &= -3.76715 + 1.92944 \log D^* - 0.09815 (\log D^*)^2 \\ &\quad - 0.00575 (\log D^*)^3 + 0.00056 (\log D^*)^4, \\ R_2 &= \log \left(1 - \frac{1 - S_f}{0.85} \right) - (1 - S_f)^{2.3} \tanh(\log D^* - 4.6) \\ &\quad + 0.3(0.5 - S_f)(1 - S_f)^2 (\log D^* - 4.6), \\ R_3 &= \left[0.65 - \frac{S_f}{2.83} \tanh(\log D^* - 4.6) \right]^{1+(3.5-P)} - 4.6. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.13)$$

201 (iii) **Model III_V (Li *et al.* 2020)**

Q13 202 Li *et al.* (2020) modified the model of Dietrich (1982) and extended it to 320 sets of
203 platy shell fragments, with the simplified form

$$204 \quad W^* = 10^{a \log(D^*) + b \log(S_f) + c}, \quad (2.14a)$$

$$W^* = 10^{0.04165 \log(D^*) + 0.5316 \log(S_f) + 0.3891}. \quad (2.14b)$$

(iv) **Model IV_V (Alcerreca et al. 2013)**

To have a quick prediction tool, Alcerreca et al. (2013) developed a model of settling velocity based on 1557 calcareous sand grains as

$$Re = \left(\sqrt{22 + 1.13D^{*2}} - 4.67 \right)^{3/2}. \quad (2.15)$$

Equation (2.15) can be rewritten in the form of settling velocity as

$$\omega = Re \frac{v}{D_n} = \frac{v}{D_n} \left(\sqrt{22 + 1.13D^{*2}} - 4.67 \right)^{3/2}. \quad (2.16)$$

2.2.3. Performance metric

In this paper, the RMSE is used as a metric for evaluating the performance of different models:

$$RMSE(\%) = \left(\frac{\sum (\text{Estimated} - \text{Measured})^2}{\sum (\text{Measured})^2} \right)^{0.5} \times 100. \quad (2.17)$$

A smaller RMSE value indicates better model performance.

2.3. Experimental set-up

A series of experiments was conducted to study the settling motion of the coral grains at the Hydraulic Engineering Laboratory, Changsha University of Science and Technology, China. A Plexiglas tank (0.3 m wide, 0.3 m long and 0.8 m deep) was designed for the test, and the tank was filled with water at temperature 24 ± 3 °C, density $\rho = 1000$ kg m⁻³ and dynamic viscosity $\mu = 1.247 \times 10^{-3}$ Pa s. The water depth in the tank was maintained at 0.80 m in the experiments. Since there are pores in the dry coral grains, bubbles will be generated from the particles when they settle down. To avoid the influence of bubbles on the settling motion, dry coral grains were immersed in the water for 24 h before testing. There was a minimum relaxation time of 5 min between each experiment, to ensure the water is truly still in the tank before the next run. The coral grain was cleaned from the bottom after each experiment such that it will not occupy the volume in the tank to increase the water depth.

Figure 5 shows the experimental set-up. The background water in the tank was illuminated using a continuous laser sheet, and the light source had wavelength 532 nm (Laserwave, G2000). Black curtains were placed around the tank to eliminate wall reflections. The settling motion of a coral grain in the water was recorded with two high-speed cameras (FASTCAM Mini UX100 and MEMRECAM HX-7S) in two orthogonal directions (see figure 5a). Both cameras were equipped with AF50 mmf/1.8DI camera lenses (Nikon, Japan) and had resolution 1024 × 1024 pixels. Raw images were recorded at 50 Hz, which was controlled by computer image capture software (Photron Motion Tools). The camera was calibrated by the MATLAB toolbox ‘camera calibrator’.

The volume of interest was a cuboid measuring 0.30 m × 0.30 m × 0.25 m (see figure 5b). To reconstruct the settling process of the coral grains, the algorithm for particle filtering was implemented in MATLAB, for which the regionprops library was used. The positions of a coral grain in settling were tracked (in MATLAB) from images taken at every moment (figure 6). After the particle had undergone the initial acceleration phase (Heisinger, Newton & Kanso 2014), it entered the vertical force equilibrium phase (see

Figure 5. (a) Image of experimental set-up for monitoring the settling motion of coral grains by a charge-coupled device (CCD) camera (in the X and Y directions, respectively), (b) Sketch of the acrylic tank in (a). The volume ($30\text{ cm} \times 30\text{ cm} \times 25\text{ cm}$) monitored by the two cameras is shaded in grey. A coral sand particle was released from the point O without initial velocity.

Figure 6. An example of the settling trajectory of a particle tracked by the particle filtering algorithm based on MATLAB. White dots in each image represent the historical particle positions, and each dot was processed from one image. The green dot in each image represents the particle position at the moment.

244 figure 7). Each particle was tested five times. The terminal settling velocity of the particle
 245 was calculated by averaging velocities of the five repeated runs. The relative error (2.18)
 246 for all the cases in the present work is less than 5%, demonstrating the repeatability of
 247 experiments (see table 4).

$$248 \quad Q_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^5 \left| \frac{\omega_j - \omega}{\omega} \right|}{5} \times 100\%. \quad (2.18)$$

249 The lengths of the long, middle and short axes (D_l , D_m and D_s , respectively) were
 250 measured by the following procedure. Specifically, following fluorescence microscopy
 251 (OLYMPUS BX43), the grain was first placed on the microscope stage and a photograph

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Figure 7. Typical time history of the settling velocity of a coral grain with $D_n = 2.63$ mm.

No.	ω_1 (cm s ⁻¹)	ω_2 (cm s ⁻¹)	ω_3 (cm s ⁻¹)	ω_4 (cm s ⁻¹)	ω_5 (cm s ⁻¹)	ω (cm s ⁻¹)	Relative error Q
1	16.383	15.851	15.822	16.839	16.057	16.190	2.08 %
2	21.441	21.758	21.617	20.872	21.258	21.389	1.21 %
3	15.118	15.937	14.871	15.296	15.342	15.312	1.71 %
4	19.378	18.823	18.750	19.6875	20.588	19.445	2.85 %
5	12.963	13.315	13.581	12.806	12.683	13.069	2.32 %
6	8.237	8.075	8.004	8.209	8.707	8.246	2.23 %
7	23.248	23.273	22.336	23.583	22.833	23.054	1.63 %
8	26.335	27.225	25.779	26.495	26.301	26.427	1.31 %
9	20.952	21.003	21.501	20.725	21.193	21.074	1.03 %
10	13.797	12.356	14.518	13.297	14.234	13.640	4.77 %

Table 4. Relative error of repeated tests for a case.

252 was taken of it. After this, the grain was rotated about the axis along which the distance
 253 across the particle is visually longest. Then another photograph was taken of this newly
 254 positioned grain. Repeating this process produces multi-angle photographs. In each
 255 photograph, the length and width of the grain can be determined through two approaches
 256 in OpenCV (Zingg 1935; Wang *et al.* 2018) as illustrated in figure 8. Specifically, the
 257 length and width can be determined through the minimum outer rectangle measurement
 258 (figure 8a) or the best fitting ellipse measurement (figure 8b). The largest length among
 259 these photographs was defined as the long axis length D_l . Among widths in these
 260 photographs, the longest one was defined as the middle axis length D_m whereas the
 261 shortest one was considered as the short axis length D_s .

262 A total of 222 experiments were conducted to investigate the settling motion of coral
 263 grains. The experimental particles conform to the coral and gastropod grains described in
 264 de Kruijf *et al.* (2021). Coral grains were sieved into 10 groups using 10 sieve shakers with
 265 sieve numbers ranging from 0.25 mm to 5 mm. To measure the density of coral grains, a
 266 set of coral grains with total mass 100 g was picked from one of groups. The volume of

Q14 Figure 8. Determination of three ellipsoid axes based on image recognition. (a) Approach of the best-fit ellipse of ImageJ from Wang *et al.* (2018). (b) Approach of the minimum bounding rectangle from Chen *et al.* (2022).

Q15 Figure 9. (a) Mapping coral grains classified by the method of Sneed & Folk (1958) into the parameter space defined by Zingg (1935). (b) Mapping coral grains classified by the method of Wang *et al.* (2019) into the parameter space defined by Zingg (1935).

267 this set of grains was measured through the drainage method. In such a way, the density
 268 for this set of grains was determined according to $\rho = M/V$. Repeating this process for
 269 each group of sieved coral grains yielded individual densities. Averaging these 10 densities
 270 gives the real density (2700 kg m⁻³) for these mixed coral grains.

271 In our experiments, the coral grains classified by Zingg (1935) and Wang *et al.* (2019)
 272 are both mapped out in the parameter space defined by Sneed & Folk (1958) in figure 9.
 273 Wide ranges of D_n (1.47–5.23 mm) and S_f (0.22–0.99) were examined (see figures 10 and
 274 11), which covered the nominal diameter range of Hongbing, Sun & Cheng (2006) for the
 275 Nansha Islands. The distribution of the range of shape coefficients for different shapes of
 276 coral sand particles is shown in figure 11.

277 Note that all the symbols used in this paper are summarised in the Appendix.

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Figure 10. Distribution of nominal diameter D_n for a total of 222 grains. Here, μ is the mean and σ is the standard deviation.

Figure 11. Proportion of each type of coral grain within each interval of shape factor S_f . A total of 222 coral grains were classified by the methods of (a) Sneed & Folk (1958), (b) Zingg (1935), and (c) Wang *et al.* (2019).

278 **3. Results**

279 **3.1. Classification of descent regimes of coral grains**

280 With laboratory experiments, three regimes of settling motion are classified for coral
 281 grains based on the reconstructed three-dimensional settling trajectory, the spiral radius
 282 r defined as

283
$$r = \sqrt{X^2 + Y^2}, \tag{3.1}$$

284 and the spectrum of settling velocity (see figure 12). The regime classification is based
 285 on the fully developed motion for which the settling velocity reaches an equilibrium state.
 286 The three regimes, namely, fluttering, tumbling and chaotic are similar to those identified
 287 for spherical (Raaghav *et al.* 2022) and disk-like particles (Field *et al.* 1997).

288 The fluttering regime is characterised by a three-dimensional spiral trajectory about a
 289 vertical axis (see figure 12a). The projection of the trajectory in the x - y plane forms an
 290 elliptical path (figure 12a). This elliptical path is further demonstrated by figure 12(b),
 291 where the normalised spiral radius r/r_{max} first increases and then decreases with time,
 292 with values of r/r_{max} equal at two ends of t/t_{max} (figure 12b). The spiral forms oscillations

Figure 12. Regime classification of settling trajectory. (a,d,g,j) Reconstructed three-dimensional trajectory with the projections of trajectory in different planes, with $D^* = 49, 72, 90, 75$, $W^* = 6.5, 9.6, 7.2, 4.0$ and $S_T = 0.84, 0.74, 0.40, 0.22$. (b,e,h,k) Variation of normalised spiral radius with time. (c,f,i,l) Spectra of velocities in the x and y directions. Fluttering, tumbling and chaotic regimes are characterised by a spiral trajectory in (a), sideways drifting in (d,g), and a chaotic trajectory in (j), respectively.

293 in both the x-z and y-z planes, with wavelength approximately $120D_n$ (figure 12a). The
 294 oscillations in these two planes are indicated by two dominant peaks ($f = 0.58, 0.78$ Hz)
 295 respectively in the spectra of velocities on the x and y axes (see figure 12c).

296 In the tumbling regime, a grain drifts sideways when settling downwards, as shown by
 297 the three-dimensional trajectory in figures 12(d,g). The projection of the trajectory in any
 298 plane displays a path extending in a particular direction (figures 12d,g). The tumbling
 299 regime has two sub-regimes, i.e. steady drifting regime and oscillatory drifting regime.
 300 The grain purely drifts in the steady drifting regime (figure 12d), in contrast to the
 301 oscillatory drifting regime where the drifting is accompanied by small-scale oscillations
 302 with wavelength $10D_n$ (figure 12g). Consistently, the spiral radius shows a linear variation
 303 with time in the steady drifting regime (figure 12e), whereas periodic fluctuations are
 304 superimposed on the increase of r/r_{max} in the oscillatory drifting regime (figure 12h). The
 305 drifting behaviour in the tumbling regime is indicated by dominant peaks at $f \approx 0$ Hz
 306 (figures 12f,i). For the oscillatory drifting regime, another dominant peak appears at

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Q16 Figure 13. Probabilities of occurrence of fluttering (F), chaotic (C), and tumbling (T) regimes for different shapes of coral grains classified based on three previous approaches. The fifth column in (a,c,e) represents the average percentage of each regime across four different shapes of classified grains. The probability of occurrence of each regime differs between different types of grains, demonstrating the dependence of descent regimes on the geometry of grains.

307 $f = 5$ Hz in the x -velocity spectrum but not in the y -velocity spectrum (figure 12i). The
 308 oscillation occurs on only one axis (figure 12g), which distinguishes it from the fluttering
 309 regime where the spiral creates oscillations on both x and y axes (see figure 12a).

310 The chaotic regime is characterised by a random combination of drifting and spiral
 311 (figure 12j). The spiral radius fluctuates irregularly with time (figure 12k). The chaotic
 312 nature of this regime is indicated by multiple peaks spanning a broad range 1–10 Hz in the
 313 velocity spectra (figure 12l).

314 The settling regime depends on the geometry of coral grains. To demonstrate this, the
 315 coral grains are classified based on three existing approaches in figure 13.

316 First, coral grains can be classified into compact, bladed, platy and elongated by
 317 following Sneed & Folk (1958) (figures 13a,b). For bladed and elongated grains, the
 318 probabilities of occurrence of the fluttering, chaotic and tumbling regimes are close to

319 each other (figure 13a). Differently, for the platy grains, only chaotic and tumbling regimes
 320 are observed, with occurrence probabilities 60 % and 40 %, respectively (figure 13a). The
 321 highest occurrence probability (39 %) of the fluttering regime appears for compact grains.

322 **Second**, for the classification method of Zingg (1935), the probabilities of occurrence
 323 of the fluttering, chaotic and tumbling regimes approach each other for the discoid and
 324 sphere grains (figures 13c,d). For the blade grains, the occurrence probability of the chaotic
 325 regime is up to ~60 % (figure 13c). The rod grains have highest occurrence probabilities
 326 for both the fluttering and tumbling regimes (figure 13c).

327 Finally, when following the method of Wang *et al.* (2020), it is found that the occurrence
 328 probability of the chaotic regime is approximately 71 % for flake grains, with 21 % and
 329 8 % for the fluttering and tumbling regimes, respectively (figures 13e,f). In contrast, the
 330 highest probability is 56 % for the fluttering regime of the dendrite grains. For the rod and
 331 block grains, the occurrence probabilities of tumbling regimes are significantly increased
 332 relative to the other two types of grains (figure 13e).

333 The averages of probabilities of occurrence of the tumbling, chaotic and fluttering
 334 regimes across the four different types of grains are approximately 26 %, 42 % and 32 %,
 335 respectively, regardless of the classification methods applied (see figures 13a,c,e). This
 336 suggests that if one randomly picks up one coral grain, then the probabilities of occurrence
 337 of the three regimes are approximately 26 %, 42 % and 32 %, respectively.

338 Whilst the dendrite grains have the highest occurrence probability (56 %) of the
 339 fluttering regime, the flake grains have the highest probability (71 %) of occurrence of the
 340 chaotic regime. The tumbling regime occurs most likely for platy grains (36 %). Clearly,
 341 these are higher than the averaged probabilities (32 %, 42 %, 26 %) shown above. This
 342 means that classifying the grains based on existing methods to some extent can help to
 343 improve our predictive accuracy of descent regimes for a given coral grain.

3.2. Prediction of settling velocity and drag coefficient

344 In this subsection, the applicability of existing empirical models for predicting settling
 345 velocity W^* and drag coefficient C_D is demonstrated. Whilst the models of settling
 346 velocity are based mostly on dimensionless diameter D^* and the Corey shape factor S_f ,
 347 the models of drag coefficient are based primarily on the Reynolds number Re and shape
 348 parameters. Therefore, to validate these models in predicting the settling velocity and the
 349 drag coefficient, we start by demonstrating the dependencies of W^* on D^* and S_f , and C_D
 350 on Re and S_f , with experimental measurements in figure 14, which provides a physical
 351 basis for applying these models.

352 Figure 14(a) shows that the settling velocity generally increases with D^* and S_f . For the
 353 same D^* , for instance $D^* = 80$, with increasing S_f from 0 to 1, the settling velocity can
 354 even vary from 4 to 10 by a factor of 2. This suggests that the settling velocity increases
 355 as the shape of a particle increasingly approaches the sphere. This velocity becomes less
 356 sensitive to the particle shape with increasing D^* . The data points in the chaotic regime set
 357 the lower limit of W^* when $D^* < 80$ and $S_f \rightarrow 0$. This implies that a non-spherical coral
 358 grain in the chaotic regime generally has lower settling velocity relative to that in the
 359 other two regimes when $D^* < 80$.

360 In contrast, the drag coefficient generally decreases with Re and S_f (figure 14b). The
 361 measured data are in agreement with those predicted by model III_D of Wang *et al.*
 362 (2018). The decreasing trend of C_D with Re is consistent with previous work about flow
 363 past a stationary plate and sphere (e.g. Almedeij 2008; Duan, He & Duan 2015) in the
 364

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Figure 14. (a) The variation of settling velocity with the dimensionless diameter and shape factor, (b) The variation of drag coefficient with the particle Reynolds number and shape factor. The result from the model of Wang et al. (2018) is incorporated in (b) for comparison. In both (a,b), the symbols are differentiated by different regimes. Whilst the dependence of settling velocity on W^* and S_f is demonstrated in (a), the relationship of drag coefficient with Re and S_f is confirmed in (b).

365 range $Re \sim O(10^2-10^3)$. There are some data points deviating from this predicted curve,
 366 which are mostly from the chaotic regime and at two ends of S_f . This is expected since
 367 there are complex self-rotations superimposed on the vertical settling motion (observed in
 368 experiments) for these deviated data points, which may suppress the shear layer separation
 369 from the grain surface and hence reduce the form drag of the grain.

370 With the demonstrated dependencies of W^* and C_D above, we now can validate the
 371 existing models by presenting comparisons between the measurements and predictions of
 372 velocity and drag coefficient in figure 15. In the comparisons, we retain the velocity forms
 373 including W^* , ω and Re , as presented originally in these velocity models.

374 There is a large difference in the prediction accuracy among different velocity models.
 375 First, model I_V of Riazi et al. (2020) provides the best prediction of settling velocity
 376 ω with RMSE = 15.9% (figure 15a). In comparison to the other three types of grains,
 377 model I_V provides less good predictions of ω for the rod grains. While model I_V largely
 378 overpredicts the velocity, model II_V of Dietrich (1982) generally underpredicts W^* using
 379 constant $P = 3$, with RMSE = 18.9% (figure 15b). Similar to model I_V, this model II_V
 380 predicts the velocity of rod grains less well.

381 Also, model III_V of Li et al. (2020) increasingly underpredicts ω with increasing ω
 382 (figure 15b). This model gives good prediction of ω for very low $S_f < 0.2$ and the flake
 383 grains, but highly underestimates ω for high S_f (figure 15b). The overall performance of
 384 this model (RMSE = 70.7%) is less good than for models I_V and II_V. This is expected
 385 given that this model was developed for platy grains in Li et al. (2020). Finally, model
 386 IV_V of Alcerreca et al. (2013) also shows good performance in predicting Re in which
 387 ω is embedded, with RMSE = 29.4% (figure 15d). Specifically, this model predicts Re very
 388 well when $S_f > 0.5$, but overpredicts ω for $S_f < 0.5$.

389 Figure 15(e) presents a comparison between different models for estimating drag
 390 coefficients, combined with predictions of Smith & Cheung (2002) by using (2.5) and
 391 (2.9). The results of model I_D (direct measurements) agree well with the predictions of
 392 Smith & Cheung (2002). Model II_D of Riazi et al. (2020) provides a nearly constant

Q17 Figure 15. Comparison between the measured and predicted settling velocity in (a–d) and drag coefficient in
 Q18 (e). There is a large difference in the prediction accuracy among different velocity and drag models. (a) Model
 I_V (Riazi et al. 2020). (b) Model II_V (Dietrich 1982). (c) Model III_V (Li et al. 2020). (d) Model IV_V
 (Alcerreca et al. 2013). (e) C_D versus Re .

393 predicted value 0.7, which is below the mean value (0.89) of model I_D. The results of
 394 model III_D of Wang et al. (2018) are in good agreement with those of model I_D for high
 395 $S_f > 0.5$, but are higher than measured C_D for low $S_f < 0.5$.

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Figure 16. Comparison between the measured and predicted settling velocity by (a) the new model (3.2), and (b) the new model (3.4). The new models perform better than the original models in figures 15(c,d).

396 Figure 14 shows the dependence of the model performance on S_f and D^* . This informs
 397 us how to improve the predicting accuracy of these models. For instance, we have
 398 demonstrated in figure 14(a) the increasing trend of W^* with S_f and D^* . These two
 399 variables are already incorporated into model III_V in (2.14). However, figure 15(c) shows
 400 that model III_V of Li *et al.* (2020) increasingly underpredicts W^* with the increase of
 401 W^* . This suggests that the empirical coefficient associated with S_f and D^* in the model
 402 needs to be modified to better reflect the dependence of W^* on S_f and D^* . Following this,
 403 we refine the empirical coefficients a , b and c in (2.14a) by using least squares regression
 404 based on our experimental data, which gives a newly modified model as

$$405 \quad W^* = 10^{0.47 \log D^* + 0.47 \log S_f + 0.083}. \quad (3.2)$$

406 Figure 16(a) shows that the performance of the newly modified model (3.2) is significantly
 407 improved with RMSE = 21.1 %, which is much lower than RMSE = 70.7 % for model
 408 III_V of Li *et al.* (2020).

409 Similarly, as the performance of model IV_V of Alcerreca *et al.* (2013) is strongly
 410 dependent on the value of S_f (see figure 15d), incorporating S_f into model IV_V will
 411 improve the model performance. Following this, we propose here a new form of velocity
 412 model as

$$413 \quad Re = S_f^a \left(\sqrt{22 + bD^{*2}} - c \right)^{3/2}. \quad (3.3)$$

414 This form is similar to model IV_V of Alcerreca *et al.* (2013) but with a newly added term
 415 S_f^a . The unknown parameters a , b and c in this extended model can be determined by using
 416 least squares regression, which gives the new model as

$$417 \quad Re = S_f^{0.417} \left(\sqrt{22 + 0.932D^{*2}} + 4.804 \right)^{3/2}. \quad (3.4)$$

418 It is seen that the performance of this model (3.4) is significantly improved (figure 16b).
 419 The value of RMSE is down to 13.2 %, which is much lower than the value for model
 420 IV_V (figure 15d).

421 In summary, it is more convenient to adopt the drag model II_D as it requires only the
 422 input of the nominal diameter of a particle and the kinematic viscosity of fluid. In contrast,

Figure 17. (a) The variation of settling velocity with the dimensionless diameter; (b) The variation of drag coefficient with the Reynolds number. Symbols are differentiated by different types of grains as classified based on the method of Wang *et al.* (2019).

423 model III_D needs to run an iterative solution between multiple equations in (2.7). Model
 424 II_D also outperforms model III_D (figure 15e). Regarding prediction of settling velocity,
 425 it is recommended to use our extended model (3.4) due to its simplicity of calculation and
 426 the highest accuracy (RMSE = 13.2%; see figure 16b).

427 4. Discussion

428 4.1. Dependence of settling velocity on the grain type

429 In § 3.1, we demonstrated the dependence of descent regimes on the grain type. One may
 430 hypothesise that the settling velocity should also have dependency on the grain type. To
 431 check this hypothesis, we have mapped our experimental data of settling velocity and drag
 432 coefficient into the W^*-D^* and $Re-C_D$ parameter spaces, respectively, in figures 17(a,b).
 433 Whilst the flake grains generally have lowest velocity, the block grains generally have
 434 the highest velocity (see figure 17a). On the contrary, the block grains generally have the
 435 smallest drag coefficient, and the flake grains generally have the largest drag coefficient
 436 (figure 17b). The data points of the flake grains are separated from the main body of
 437 data points (see figure 17b). Therefore, figure 17 demonstrates the dependency of settling
 438 velocity and drag coefficient on the grain type.

439 This demonstrated dependency informs us in developing a specified model for each
 440 type of grain. These models take the form of (2.14). The coefficients of a , b and c are
 441 again determined by least squares regression based on our experimental data, as detailed
 442 in table 5. It is seen that the specified models for each type of grain have different levels
 443 of predictive performance. In comparison to the model of Li *et al.* (2020), the modified
 444 model for flake grains has achieved much better performance with only RMSE = 5.9%
 445 (see table 5). The significantly improved predictability for the flake grains suggests that to
 446 have better predictive capacity, it is possible to categorise the coral grains first and then
 447 develop a model for each type of grain.

Coefficient	All data	Block	Dendrite	Flake	Rod
a	0.47	0.479	0.286	0.532	0.369
b	0.47	0.532	0.314	0.464	0.015
c	0.083	0.071	0.421	-0.058	0.155
RMSE	21.1 %	19.4 %	5.9 %	11.20 %	16.6 %

Table 5. Modified models (in the form of (2.14)) for each type of grain for predicting the dimensionless settling velocity W^* .

448 5. Conclusions

449 In this paper, a series of laboratory experiments was conducted to investigate the settling
 450 motion of 222 coral grains. The geometry of these grains was measured by the image
 451 recognition technique, the grain density was measured with the drainage method, and the
 452 settling trajectory was reconstructed through particle-filtering-based object tracking.

453 Three descent regimes of settling motions, namely, fluttering, chaotic and tumbling,
 454 were classified based on the reconstructed three-dimensional trajectory, the variation of
 455 spiral radius with time, and the velocity spectra. The fluttering regime is characterised by
 456 a three-dimensional spiral trajectory; in the tumbling regime, the particle drifts sideways
 457 when it settles downwards. This regime includes two sub-regimes, i.e. the steady drifting
 458 regime where the particle purely drifts, and the oscillatory drifting regime in which
 459 small-scale oscillations are superimposed on the drifting process. The chaotic regime is
 460 characterised by a random combination of drifting and spiral motions.

461 By using existing classification methods, the 222 coral grains were categorised into
 462 different types of grains. We have presented the probability of occurrence of each regime
 463 for each type of grain. Based on the 222 data sets, we have demonstrated that if one
 464 randomly picks up one coral grain, then the probabilities of occurrence of the tumbling,
 465 chaotic and fluttering regimes are approximately 26 %, 42 % and 32 %, respectively.

466 We then show that, first, the dimensionless settling velocity generally increases with the
 467 non-dimensional diameter D^* and Corey shape factor S_f , and second, the drag coefficient
 468 generally decreases with the Reynolds number Re and S_f . The demonstrated dependencies
 469 of W^* and C_D provide a physical basis for applying existing empirical models of settling
 470 velocity and drag coefficient to coral grains considered herein. The applicability of a range
 471 of models of settling velocity and drag coefficient was then validated against the 222 coral
 472 grains. It is found that the performance of these models depends on the grain geometry.
 473 For instance, the velocity model of Alcerreca *et al.* (2013) and the drag model of Wang
 474 *et al.* (2018) perform less well for the grains with low values of S_f .

475 We have made improvements in the predictive capacity of settling velocity. First, we
 476 have extended the models of Li *et al.* (2020) and Alcerreca *et al.* (2013), which gives two
 477 new models with much better performance. Second, we modified the model of Li *et al.*
 478 (2020) for each type of grain, including, block, dendrite, flake and rod. This provides an
 479 idea of how to improve the predictive capacity of settling velocity through pre-categorising
 480 the grains.

481 In a future study, the objective could be adopting second- or third-order shape
 482 descriptors to replace the first-order shape descriptors (the Corey shape factor) in the
 483 settling velocity models. In experiments, it may be possible to take macro-photographs
 484 of coral particles to obtain information about the rotation movement of the coral particles
 485 during settlement. However, the filming range has to be reduced because of the limited

486 range of pixels of the camera. Using multiple cameras simultaneously may solve this
487 problem.

Q19 488 **Supplementary material.** Supplementary material is available at <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2024.469>.

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494 **Declaration of interests.** The authors report no conflict of interest.

495 **Data availability statement.** The data for experimental results (i.e. shape characteristics, settling velocity
496 and classification results of coral grains) of this study are openly available at <https://datadryad.org/stash/share/atsTCBGvDIMeirFyfMgmaQxceYnKly5HfiIXv9P4Src>.

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Q20 502 **Appendix. Definition sketches**

A	Area of image
$A_{eq, sph}$	Surface area of volume-equivalent sphere
A_{ell}	Surface area of irregular particles
A_s	Surface area of particle
A_P	Projected area
C_A	Area of minimum convex hull
C_D	Drag coefficient
$C_{D, sph}$	Drag coefficient of spherical particle
C_P	Perimeter of minimum convex hull
D_A	Diameter of circle with same area as projection area of particle
D_{disk}	Diameter of disk
D_P	Diameter of circle with same perimeter as image
D_l	Longest orthogonal dimension of particle
D_m	Intermediate orthogonal dimension of particle
D_s	Shortest orthogonal dimension of particle
D_n	Nominal diameter of particle
$D_{eq, sph}$	Diameter of volume-equivalent sphere
D_{sg}	Sphere diameter
D^*	Dimensionless diameter
F_a	Distance between two parallel tangents of particle at arbitrary angle
g	Gravitational acceleration
Ga	Galileo number
h	Thickness of disk

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I_p	Moment of inertia
I^*	Dimensionless moment of inertia
L	Maximum Feret diameter
P	Roundness of particle
P_i	Perimeter of image
$P_{p, max}$	Perimeter of maximum projection area of particle
P_{eq}	Perimeter of circle of equal maximum projection area
R_0	Roundness
Re	Particle Reynolds number
S	Specific gravity of particle
S_A	Superficial area
S_{CA}	Superficial area of convex hull
S_0	Convexity ratio
S_P	Relative sphericity
S_f	Shape factor of particles
T	Minimum Feret diameter
V	Volume of coral grain
V_P	Particle volume
W	Median Feret diameter
W^*	Dimensionless settling velocity
X	Inverse circularity
ρ	Density of water
ρ_s	Density of coral grain
ω	Particle settling velocity
ν	Kinematic viscosity of ambient water
μ	Dynamic viscosity of water
χ	Aspect ratio
Ψ	Ratio of sphericity

503

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